

Chemical Constituents of *Cannabis sativa*

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Cannabis sativa Linn. (Cannabaceae), popularly known as *Bhang/Ganja/Charas* in Bengal, finds application in several medicinal preparations and its activity is ascribed due to alcoholic and phenolic acids. Earlier investigation of this species resulted in the characterisation of number of compounds¹. The present chemical analysis of *C. sativa* culminated in the isolation of friedelin, epifriedelinol, 4-hydroxymethyl and propyl benzoates, 30-nor-9,19-cyclolanost-24-methylene-3 β -acetate (1) and stearic acid of which the latter three compounds are being reported for the first time from this species.

The whole plant of *C. sativa* was Soxhletted with petrol (b.p. 60–80°) for 24 h and the concentrated extract was chromatographed over silica gel with solvents of increasing polarity using hexane and acetone. Hexane-acetone (49 : 1) eluted 1 while the latter hexane-acetone (9 : 1) eluates yielded friedelin (m.p. 266°) and epifriedelinol (m.p. 277–79°) after crystallisation. The mother liquors obtained after the crystallisation of both friedelin and epifriedelinol were further chromatographed to afford 4-hydroxy-n-propylbenzoate (2a) and 4-hydroxymethylbenzoate (2b).

The hexane-acetone (7 : 3) eluates of the main chromatogram on purification gave stearic acid from hexane-acetone (19 : 1) eluates. The structures of 1, 2a and 2b were arrived at from the analysis of their ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral data and of friedelin, epifriedelinol and stearic acid by their direct comparison with the authentic samples.

30-Nor-9,19-cyclolanost-24-methylene-3 β -acetate (1) : It was obtained as an amorphous solid, ν_{\max} (thin liquid film) 3 100, 3 060, 1 740, 1 648, 1 245 and 878 cm^{-1} ; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃, 200 MHz) 0.14, 0.38 (1H, d each, *J* 4.27, 4.16 Hz, H₂-19), 0.83 (3H, d, *J* 6.13 Hz, H-28), 0.88 (3H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, H-21), 0.89 (3H, s, H-30), 0.96 (3H, s, H-18), 1.01 (3H, d, *J* 6.84 Hz, H-26), 1.02 (3H, d, *J* 6.84 Hz, H-27), 2.04 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 4.65, 4.70 (1H, d each, *J* 1.4 Hz, =CH₂); ¹³C nmr δ (CDCl₃; 50 MHz) 30.4 (t, C-1), 30.9(t, C-2), 78.7(d, C-3), 41.5(d, C-4), 43.4 (d, C-5), 24.6(t, C-6), 28.1(t, C-7), 46.9(d, C-8), 23.6(s, C-9), 29.3(s, C-10), 25.0(t, C-11), 35.3(t, C-12), 45.3(s, C-13), 48.8(s, C-14), 32.8(t, C-15), 26.9(t, C-16), 52.1(d, C-17), 17.8 (q, C-18), 27.1(t, C-19), 36.1(d, C-20), 18.3(q, C-21), 34.9(t, C-22), 31.3(t, C-23), 156.9(s, C-24), 33.7(d, C-25), 21.8(q, C-26), 22.0(q, C-27), 19.1(q, C-28), 14.4(q, C-29), 105.9(t,

C-31), 171.0(s, OCOCH₃), 21.3 (q, OCOCH₃); *m/z* (rel. int.) 468 (M⁺, 0.4), 408 (5.9), 393 (4.6), 175 (4.5), 107 (19.4), 105 (17), 93 (17.6), 83 (12.2), 69 (38.8), 43 (100). It was identified as 30-nor-9,19-cyclolanost-24-methylene-3 β -acetate (1)².

4-Hydroxy-n-propylbenzoate (2a) : It was crystallised from petrol-CH₂Cl₂ mixture, m.p. 98–99° (lit.³ 96.2–98°); *R_f* 0.11 (petrol : ether, 4 : 1; Si-gel G (Merck)); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 280, 1 678, 1 608, 1 590, 1 520, 1 230, 852 and 780 cm^{-1} ; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 1.02 (3H, t, *J* 7.4 Hz, H₃-3'), 1.77 (2H, m, H₂-2'), 4.27 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, H₂-1'), 6.76 (1H, br s, OH), 6.90 (2H, dd each, *J* 8.2 Hz, H-3, H-5), 7.96 (2H, dd each, *J* 8.2 Hz, H-2, H-6); ¹³C nmr δ (CDCl₃) 122.5(s, C-1), 131.86(d, C-2, C-6), 115.22(d, C-3, C-5), 160.5(s, C-4), 66.5(t, C-1'), 22.0(t, C-2'), 10.4(q, C-3') and 167.5(s, COO); *m/z* (rel. int.) 180 (M⁺, 12.9), 138(66.1), 122(12.6), 121(100), 106(6.5), 94(2.6), 93(23.2), 65(33.6), 42(1.6), 41(6.5).

4-Hydroxymethylbenzoate (2b) : It was crystallised from a mixture of petrol-CH₂Cl₂, C₈H₈O₃, m.p. 127–28° (lit.³ 131°); *R_f* 0.09 (petrol : ether, 4 : 1; Si-gel G (Merck)), and identified from the spectral data

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